

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Comprehensive Review of Triphala as an Herbal Ingredient in Skin Care System

Syed Imran, Geetha Bandi, Laxmi Patil, Mohammed Usman Chikkerur*, Prajwal Bhosage, Y V Vijayananditha

Sri Raghavendra College of Pharmacy, Chitradurga, Karnataka, India 577501

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 14 Jan 2026

Keywords:

Intrinsic aging, Extrinsic aging, Anti-aging cream, Triphala

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.18246062

ABSTRACT

Aging of organs is natural process in body; skin as a part of body shows visible sign for aging. Intrinsic aging is true aging; it is primarily due to alterations in the body. Extrinsic aging is caused by UVA and UVB radiations, that lead to gross disorganisation of the skin matrix. purpose of this review to focus on design, develop and physicochemical evaluation of Anti-aging cream. Creams were created for this study is based on plant origin powder known as Triphala. Its Antioxidant and Antiaging properties were identified by referring various research studies. The formulation is water in oil type of emulsion which undergone several tests to evaluate the formulation safety and appearance. The formulation may give young and beautiful skin which considered to be positive influence on people, social behaviour and reproductive status.

INTRODUCTION

Aging

Signs of dermal aging, such wrinkles and skin relaxation, are common in today's big population. There are numerous etiological factors of skin aging but primarily classified into two factors external (exogenous) and internal (endogenous).

Exogenous factors include things like smoking, exposure to harmful chemicals, wind exposure, and UV radiation, whereas endogenous factors are

mostly the accumulation of time and physiological characteristics. ^[1]

Skin, the largest organ, protects the body from radiation, bacteria, toxins, and pollution by acting as the primary barrier between the internal and exterior surroundings. The reduction and eventual stoppage of keratinocyte and fibroblast cell division within the skin is what causes skin aging. Skin gets drier and less elastic under these circumstances. due to the extracellular matrix becoming denaturated, which causes wrinkles to

*Corresponding Author: Mohammed Usman Chikkerur

Address: Sri Raghavendra College of Pharmacy, Chitradurga, Karnataka, India 577501

Email ✉: usmanck402@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

appear. takes place on skin in both exposed and non-exposed areas of incident UV radiation. [2]

What is meant by "reactive oxygen species" is the outcome of normal cellular metabolism. In mitochondria, ROS are generated when oxygen consumption falls between 1% and 5%. The increased ROS diminish the function of mitochondria that leads elevated DNA damage and mutation or sudden change in gene, the chain reaction leads dermal aging.

In other side air borne pollutants also contributing to skin aging. Ozone, nitrogen dioxide, and sulphur dioxide are known to enhance skin oxidative stress (SOS), It, in turn, alters the skin's protective function and reduces antioxidant activity. [3]

In addition, the skin produces antimicrobial peptides, has a specific microbial ecology, and goes through a number of inflammatory and immunological processes. Additionally, our body's physical barrier shields us against a variety of chemical, physical, and environmental threats. Therefore, the skin itself is crucial in preventing natural skin aging. As people age, their skin's various layers—the dermis, adipose tissue, muscle, and epidermis—change in composition and characteristics. As we age, our skin begins to lose proteins and elastin fibers. They are the fundamental components that give skin its health, fit, brightness, and suppleness. [4]

Figure No.1 Mechanism of Photoaging

1. Anti-aging effect of triphala

Numerous in-vitro, in-vivo, and human investigations have demonstrated that triphala can increase antioxidant levels and reduce lipid peroxidation. The inclusion of flavonoids, polyphenols, and vitamin C is associated with the antioxidant properties of our formulation. Triphala's active ingredient lowers ROS levels, which lessens oxidative stress. That could demonstrate the antiaging effects. [5]

2. Topical drug delivery

Topical delivery medication is the process of applying a drug-containing formulation to the skin in order to directly treat a cutaneous condition or the cutaneous manifestation of a systemic disease. The objective is to limit the pharmacological effects of the medication either within or on the skin's surface. Although foams, although medicated transdermal adhesive systems, powders, sprays, and solutions are commonly employed, semisolid formulation is the most commonly used topical delivery route.

Advantages of using medicine topically:

- Convenient and easy for application
- This route avoids the first pass metabolism
- Avoid of risk.

3. Cream

Creams are topical medications that are administered to the skin's outermost layer. A "viscous liquid or semisolid emulsion of either the oil-in-water or water-in-oil type" mode of administration with variable oil and water contents is referred to as a cream.

Creams are used to protect, cleanse, and enhance the look of the skin. and give therapeutic effect for various skin conditions such as psoriasis, fungal infections, inflammation. These topical preparations are applied to the skin's afflicted regions to provide a local impact.

Every medical system, including allopathic and ayurveda (herbal) medicine, has creams that individuals use for various skin conditions. Following are the types of creams.

- Creams that include oil droplets dispersed across a continuous phase or dispersion medium, such water, are referred to as oil in water (O/W).
- Water in oil (W/O) creams are composed of water droplets dispersed across an oil-based continuous phase or dispersion medium. [6]

Triphala

Triphala is an old ayurvedic powdered mixture used in Indian medicine. Triphala means the three fruits. synonyms of triphala are Sresthatamam, vara, phalatrikam. Triphala is powdered herbal preparation used in many disorders.

The fruits Terminalia chebula Retz. (Haritaki), Terminalia bellerica Roxb. (vibhitaki), and

Emmalia officinalis. (amalaki) are combined to make triphala, one of the most popular ayurvedic remedies. Usually, the mixture has the same quantity of the myrobalans listed. Triphala is a common preparation in Ayurveda. In the traditional Indian medical practice, it is referred to as Tridoshik rasayana in Ayurvedic texts and is a therapeutic agent that balances the vata, pitta, and kapha parts of the Ayurvedic constitution. Empress officinalis Gaertn, often known as amalaki, is chilly in nature, whilst Terminalia chebula Retz and Terminalia bellarica Roxb or vibhitaki are warm. Since triphala is a balanced blend of vibhitaki, haritaki, and amalaki, it may be used as an internal cleanser and gut detoxifier. Ancient Ayurvedic scriptures mention triphala as a herbal supplement. The Samhitas of Charaka and Sushruta.[7]

Terminalia chebula (haritaki)

Figure No.2 Terminalia chebula (haritaki)

In Latin, Terminalia chebula Linn. The family Combretaceae includes it. Haimavati, Shiva, Avyatha, Pathya, Abhaya, Haritaki, and Vayastha are some examples of traditional names. English Chebulic Myrobalan. Fruits were used as parts in haritaki.

Habit (Swaroop): large, intermediate-sized deciduous tree.

Chemical composition: Contains a range of phenolic acids, such as gallic and chebulic acids, an estimated 30% of tannins, and a natural

purgative of anthraquinone. It is well known that *D. chebula* fruits contain phenolic compounds, including flavonoids, phenolic acids, and tannins. Another well-known characteristic of fruits is their high ascorbic acid (vitamin C) concentration. Corilagin, terflavin-A, terchebulic punicalgin, chebulinic acid, and chebulagic acid are the main hydrolyzable tannins. [7]

Terminalia bellerica Roxb (Vibhitaki)

Figure No.3 Terminalia bellerica (vibhitaki)

Terminalia bellerica Roxb is its Latin name. This member of the Combretaceae family is known by its traditional name, Vibhitaka. In haritaki, or Belleric Myrobalan as it is known in English, fruits were utilized as parts.

Habit of Swaroopa: Large deciduous tree

Chemical composition: Its component compounds include beta-sitosterol, mannitol, glucose, fructose, rhamnose, ellagic acid, gallic acid, lignans, flavone, anolignan B10, tannins, ellargic acid, ethyl gallate, galloyl glucose, chebulaginic acid, and phenyllembelin. The seeds contain greenish yellow oil, while the fruit has 17% tannin, gallotanic acid, and resin. [7]

Indian gooseberry (Amalaki)

Figure No.4 Indian gooseberry (Amalaki)

Its Latin name is *Embllica officinalis* Gaertn. Dhatri Amalaki is the traditional name for amla, which belongs to the Euphorbiaceae family. Its English name is Indian gooseberry. In haritaki, fruits were utilized as pieces.

Swaropa's habitat is a large deciduous tree.

Chemical makeup: Seeds include phosphopeptides, fixed oil, and an essential oil, while in this fruit vitamin C is majorly found antioxidant. Tannins are abundant in fruits, bark, and leaves. [7]

Mechanism of triphala against dermal aging

Polyphenols like gallic acid, ellagic acid, chebulinic acid, and triphala reduce oxidative stress by scavenging free radicals. which is a primary cause of aging. By transforming reactive oxygen free radicals into non-reactive compounds, tannins are produced. [3]

Figure No.5 Mechanism of triphala on aging

Pharmacological and therapeutic effects of Triphala Anticancer activity

Triphala has the ability to kill cancerous cells. Gallic acid, one of its main components, may be the cause of its suppression of cancer cell proliferation. [8]

Antioxidant activity

Triphala is well recognized for preventing Y-ray-induced damage to plasmid pBR322 DNA and microsomal lipids. By transforming reactive oxygen free radicals into nonreactive compounds, Triphala has a high content of tannins and polyphenols. The abundance of polyphenols in triphala is what gives it its radioprotective and antioxidant qualities. [9]

Triphala against stress:

Triphala as an anti-stress supplement has been demonstrated to reduce physiological and behavioural abnormalities associated with stress. [10]

Wound healing Triphala containing ointments shows significant wound healing property. The *in-*

vivo studies on triphala shown the granulation tissue shows boost the collagen, decreases bacterial count, applying triphala to wounds resulted in quicker wound healing and greater water retention. [11]

Anti-microbial activity

Triphala strictly shows anti-microbial activity on microbes including lactobacillus and streptococcus. Ayurvedic preparations like triphala mashi shows anti-microbial activity due phenolic compounds and tannins. [12]

Anti diabetic activity

Both normal and diabetic rats' serum sugar levels were considerably lowered within 4 hours of oral intake or injection of triphala extract, and regular triphala treatment demonstrated anti-diabetic effect or lowered blood sugar levels. [13,14]

Analgesic-ulcerogenic-antipyretic activity

In mice experimental models, triphala's analgesic, ulcerogenic, and antipyretic qualities were compared to those of NSAIDS indomethacin. It was shown that triphala, at both dose levels, had good analgesic and antipyretic effects without posing a risk to the GIT. [15]

Anti-inflammatory activity

Gallic acid has an anti-inflammatory impact by selectively inhibiting COX-2, according to a triphala research. Applying triphala topically helps to avoid uveitis. [16]

Anti-aging activity

Triphala extract has been demonstrated in *in vitro* experiments to have extremely protective anti-aging properties on human skin cells, including

boosting collagen and reducing hyperpigmentation.^[17]

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Excipients used in preparation of antiaging cream:

1. Aloe vera

Aloe vera, (*Aloe Barbadensis* Miller), which associated Asphodelaceae (Liliaceae) family. The succulent perennial herb aloe vera has a shallow root system, a triangular, sessile stem, and leaves that are 10 cm in width and 30 to 50 cm in length. With a pH of 4.5 and 99% water, aloe

2. Bees wax

Beeswax is a naturally occurring substance that is extracted from worker bees' abdomen wax-producing glands. The composition and colours are varying from the region to region and the diet is also responsible for composition. Also known as White beeswax, yellow beeswax. Bee wax is a refined wax that is extracted from the honeycomb of hive bees, including *Apis mellifera* Linn and other *Apis* species that are members of the Apidae family. Beeswax is a compound made of lipids. It comprises hydrocarbons, free fatty acids, unsaturated and saturated monoesters, and other materials that worker bees generate. Beeswax is resistant to numerous acids. These characteristics of beeswax making it ideal for protecting coating and barrier application.^[19]

3. Liquid paraffin (heavy)

Saturated hydrocarbons derived from petroleum make up liquid paraffin, a colorless, nearly odorless, clear greasy liquid. Petroleum has been utilized as medicinal since 400. Mineral oil, another name for liquid paraffin, is a mixture of petroleum-based liquid with straight-chain,

branch-chain, and ring structures. The chain of carbon in liquid paraffin is longer than C14. Liquid paraffin has been used into a number of cosmetic formulae, due to its remarkable skin tolerability. a large range of viscosities, superior skin protection, and cleaning efficacy.^[20,21]

4. Rose water:

Rose water obtained from Damask Rose also known as Oil Rose, Isparta rose or *Rosa damascena* Miller. It belongs to the family Rosaceae. *R. damascena* is a perennial bushy shrub with vibrant flowers. Five to seven leaflets make up the complex, imparipinnate leaves. Tunisia, Iraq, Morocco, Syria, Iran, Greece, France, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Turkey. Anthocyanins, terpenes, flavonoids, and glycosides are all present in *R. damascena*. Vitamin C, carboxylic acid, myrcene, quercetin, and kaempferol are all present in this plant. According to traditional medicine, *R. damascena*'s main beneficial benefits include reducing inflammation, particularly in the neck area, treating menstrual bleeding, treating stomachaches and chest discomfort, and treating intestinal issues. skin health, wound healing, and some allergies. In Iran, *R. damascena* produces a lot of rose water, which has between 10% and 15% rose oil in it. Triterpenoids and saponins are the four primary polyphenolic chemicals responsible for rose water's anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. Flavonoids in rose water contribute to skin radiance and are used to moisturize the skin.^[22,23,24]

5. Borax:

Wax and borax are mixed to create a variety of cosmetic goods, including gels, creams, and lotions. It is well-known for being a component in hand soaps that help remove oil or grease from hands. Borax is an ideal ingredient for cleansers and toners because of its basic nature. In cosmetic

formulations, borax is also used as a preservative for moisturizing goods to limit microbial development, as well as an emulsifier, buffering

ingredient to maintain pH, and scrub, lotion, gel, shampoo, and bath salts. [25]

Preparation of anti-aging cream:

Table No.1 Preparation of anti-aging cream

Sr. no	Ingredients	Role	Characteristics
1	Triphala	API	It is dry powdered herbal preparation obtained from the myrobalans likely haritaki, amalaki, vibhitaki
2	Beeswax	Base	Naturally occurring waxy secretion of honeybees
3	Liquid Paraffin	Emollient/ skin protective	An oily, clear liquid with no smell that comes from petroleum,
4	Aloe vera	moisturizer	99 percent of aloe vera, a triangular succulent perennial plant, is water.
5	Rose water	Toner / Perfuming agent	It is an abundant product of <i>R.damascena</i>
6	Borax	Emulsifier/ Preservative	It is a mineral salt of boric acid

Method:

Procedure for o/w emulsion cream

In single beaker, the oil-soluble components are heated to 75°C in a water bath. In a separate beaker of water, preservatives and various substances that dissolve in water also melt. Once heated. After heating, a mortar and pestle were used to gradually add the external phase to the internal phase and triturate the mixture until a clicking sound was generated. Once the temperature has cooled, preservative and perfume are applied. This recipe will include more water than oil.[6]

Procedure for w/o emulsion creams

In beaker, the emulsifier and the oil-soluble components are heated to 75°C in a water bath. In a separate beaker of water, preservatives and other materials that dissolve in water are melted. After this step, the internal phase is poured in a mortar and pestle, and then the external phase (oil phase) added gradually until a clicking sound is made. After the temperature of the mixture has decreased, the fragrance is added. In such

compositions, the dispersed phase would be very little and the continuous phase would be quite large. [26]

EVALUATION TEST FOR CREAMS:

- 1. Organoleptic Characteristics:** These characteristics including smell, appearance and colour should be observed.
- 2. pH measurement:** At room temperature, a digital pH meter (3-point calibration type) may be used to measure the pH. [27]
- 3. Homogeneity determination:** The homogeneity of the formulation can be determined by touch and the visual appearance.[28]
- 4. Irritancy test:** this test done to check whether the formulation causing redness irritation Edema or the cream is safe for application.[29]
- 5. finding a type of smear:** in this test the formulation applied on outer surface of skin to check its greasiness. Then type of smear were observed.[30]

6. Microbial growth test: Any microbial contamination in the formulation is to be detected by this test. Agar mediums were used for these tests.

- Preparation of agar plate medium
- The formulation is inoculated in agar plate by streak plate method
- Prepare the control without formulation
- Incubate for 24 hours and temperature is maintained about 37°C, this period is called incubation period.
- After that the plates with formulation compared with control plates, to observe the microbial contamination.

7. Washability: Apply a tiny bit of lotion to your palm and rinse it off with running water.

8. Assessing the capacity to spread: By sandwiching three grams of cream between two glass slides and allowing them to press to create a thin layer, one may assess the spreadability of the formulation. The weight, which should weigh around 5 grams, is put on the top slide. Weight is positioned to exert enough pressure for a predetermined amount of time (5 minutes). Using the connecting string, lift the upper slide once 10 grams of weight has been maintained. It has been observed that it takes ten centimeters to slide the upper slide. The formula to calculate spread ability is

$$S = m \times L/T^{[31]}$$

CONCLUSION

The cream, formulated with Triphala and other excipients such as Aloe vera gel, Bees wax, liquid paraffin, borax and Rose water, may show versatile effects with Triphala showing distinct significant activities such as Anti-Aging, Antioxidant, Anti-hyper Pigmentation activity,

Wound Healing. The consistency and stability of the formulation at room temperature can be evaluate by performing numerous tests for its safe application on the skin. This study focuses on safe and effective formulation of anti-aging cream containing herbal ingredients. which have seen a surge in both cosmetic and topical applications. The current cosmetic trend follows the blend of both natural and synthetic remedies use in formulation in order to accept cosmetics with trust.

REFERENCES

1. He X, Wan F, Su W, Xie W. Research progress on skin aging and active ingredients. *Molecules*. 2023 Jan;28(14):5556.
2. Hama amin Hussien N, Karem Abdulla S. Role of antioxidants in skin aging and the molecular mechanism of ROS: A comprehensive review.
3. Jaffri JM. Reactive oxygen species and antioxidant system in selected skin disorders. *The Malaysian journal of medical sciences: MJMS*. 2023 Feb 28;30(1):7.
4. Bay EY, Topal IO. Aging skin and anti-aging strategies. *Exploratory Research and Hypothesis in Medicine*. 2023 Sep 25;8(3):269-79.
5. Prasad S, Srivastava SK. Oxidative stress and cancer: chemopreventive and therapeutic role of triphala. *Antioxidants*. 2020 Jan 13;9(1):72.
6. Lalita C, Shalini G. Creams: A review on classification, preparation methods, evaluation and its applications. *JDDT*. 2020 Oct 2;10:281-9.
7. Bali Chouhan BC, Kumawat RC, Mita Kotecha MK, Ramamurthy A, Sumit Nathani SN. Triphala: a comprehensive Ayurvedic review.
8. Kaur S, Michael H, Arora S, Härkönen PL, Kumar S. The in vitro cytotoxic and apoptotic activity of Triphala—an Indian herbal drug.

- Journal of ethnopharmacology. 2005 Feb 10;97(1):15-20.
9. Sabina EP, Rasool M. An in vivo and in vitro potential of Indian ayurvedic herbal formulation Triphala on experimental gouty arthritis in mice. *Vascular pharmacology*. 2008 Jan 1;48(1):14-20.
 10. Kumar NS, Nair AS, Nair AM, Murali M. Pharmacological and therapeutic effects of triphala-A literature review. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. 2016 May 1;5(3):23.
 11. Kumar MS, Kirubanandan S, Sripriya R, Sehgal PK. Triphala promotes healing of infected full-thickness dermal wound. *Journal of Surgical Research*. 2008 Jan 1;144(1):94-101.
 12. Nair V, Arjuman A, Gopalakrishna HN, Dorababu P, Mirshad PV, Bhargavan D, Chatterji D. Evaluation of the anti-ulcer activity of NR-ANX-C (a polyherbal formulation) in aspirin & pyloric ligation induced gastric ulcers in albino rats. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*. 2010 Aug 1;132(2):218-23.
 13. Prativadibhayankaram VS, Malhotra S, Pandhi P, Singh A. Anti-diabetic activity of triphala fruit extracts, individually and in combination, in a rat model of insulin resistance. *Natural Product Communications*. 2008 Feb;3(2):1934578X0800300230.
 14. Sabu MC, Kuttan R. Anti-diabetic activity of medicinal plants and its relationship with their antioxidant property. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 2002 Jul 1;81(2):155-60.
 15. Nair V, Arjuman A, Gopalakrishna HN, Dorababu P, Mirshad PV, Bhargavan D, Chatterji D. Evaluation of the anti-ulcer activity of NR-ANX-C (a polyherbal formulation) in aspirin & pyloric ligation induced gastric ulcers in albino rats. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*. 2010 Aug 1;132(2):218-23.
 16. Rasool M, Sabina EP. Antiinflammatory effect of the Indian Ayurvedic herbal formulation Triphala on adjuvant-induced arthritis in mice. *Phytotherapy Research: An International Journal Devoted to Pharmacological and Toxicological Evaluation of Natural Product Derivatives*. 2007 Sep;21(9):889-94.
 17. Peterson CT, Denniston K, Chopra D. Therapeutic uses of triphala in ayurvedic medicine. *The Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine*. 2017 Aug 1;23(8):607-14.
 18. Pareek S, Nagaraj A, Sharma P, Naidu S, Yousuf A. Aloe-vera: a herb with medicinal properties. *IJOOCR*. 2013 Jul;1(1):47-50.
 19. Ledjanac S, Hoxha F, Jasnić N, Tasić A, Jovanović M, Blagojević S, Plavša N, Tosti T. The Influence of the Chemical Composition of Beeswax Foundation Sheets on Their Acceptability by the Bee's Colony. *Molecules*. 2024 Nov 21;29(23):5489.
 20. Sharif F, Crushell E, O'driscoll K, Bourke B. Liquid paraffin: a reappraisal of its role in the treatment of constipation. *Archives of disease in childhood*. 2001 Aug 1;85(2):121-4.
 21. Miyasaka Y, Hashizaki K, Kono Y, Taguchi H, Fujii M. Effect of the physicochemical properties of liquid paraffin on the phase state and rheological properties of lecithin reverse wormlike micelles. *Chemical and Pharmaceutical Bulletin*. 2022 Jan 1;70(1):52-6.
 22. Yildirim B, Ozcelik H. Taxonomic Studies on *Rosa damascena* Miller Complex in Türkiye and Two New Species: *Rosa stipulata*, *Rosa comantema*. *Bulletin of Pure & Applied Sciences-Botany*. 2023 Jul 1(2).
 23. Boskabady MH, Shafei MN, Saberi Z, Amini S. Pharmacological effects of *Rosa*

- damascena. Iranian journal of basic medical sciences. 2011 Jul;14(4):295.
24. Safia A, Aamir Z, Iqbal A, Rafi S, Zafar M. Assessment of rose water and evaluation of antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of a rose water based cream formulation. *Int. J. Pharm. Clin. Res.* 2019 Jan 25;11:43-8.
25. Saraf S, Kaur CD. Phytoconstituents as photoprotective novel cosmetic formulations. *Pharmacognosy reviews.* 2010 Jan;4(7):1.
26. Pal Arti PA, Soni Manish SM, Patidar Kalpana PK. Formulation and evaluation of poly herbal cream.
27. Navindgikar NN, Kamalapurkar KA, Chavan PS. Formulation and evaluation of multipurpose herbal cream. *International journal of current pharmaceutical research.* 2020 Mar 23;12(3):25-30.
28. Pankaj S, Lokeshwar T, Mukesh B, Vishnu B. Review on neem (*Azadirachta indica*): thousand problems one solution. *International research journal of pharmacy.* 2011;2(12):97-102.
29. Dhyan A, Chander V, Singh N. Formulation and evaluation of multipurpose herbal cream. *J. Drug Deliv. Ther.* 2019 Mar 15;9(2):341-3.
30. Rignall A. ICHQ1A (R2) stability testing of new drug substance and product and ICHQ1C stability testing of new dosage forms. *ICH quality guidelines: an implementation guide.* 2017 Sep 27:3-44.
31. Kamble M, Raghatate P, Meshram S. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Cold Cream using *Bombax ceiba* fruit pulp. *Int J Res Sci Innov.* 2020;7(2):184-6.

HOW TO CITE: Syed Imran, Geetha Bandi, Laxmi Patil, Mohammed Usman Chikkerur, Prajwal Bhosage, Y V Vijayananditha, A Comprehensive Review of Triphala as an Herbal Ingredient in Skin Care System, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 1, 1458-1467. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18246062>

